

Gold Drugs

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Rheumatoid arthritis, a progressive disease involving destruction of joint cartilage tissue, has been controlled in many cases over the past fifty years by the parenterally administered gold(I) compounds, e.g. gold sodium thiosulphate, $\text{Na}_2\text{Au}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2$ (*Sammocrysin*); gold disodium thiomalate, Na_2AuTm (*Myocrisin*); gold thioglucose, GTG (*Solganol*) and gold thiopolypeptides (*Aurodetoxin*). An orally administered form of gold, [(2,3,4,6-tetra-O-acetyl-1-thio- β -D-glucopyranosato-S)(triethylphosphine)gold] (*Auranofin*) is presently undergoing extensive clinical trial for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. Recent advances in biological, chemical and medical disciplines now provide better understanding of the processes whereby the gold complexes exercise their physiological and pharmacological effects, resulting in exciting new developments in their therapeutic applications.

ALTHOUGH living things have a natural requirement for some metal ions, gold, so far as is known, is not one of them. Metallic gold is exceptionally stable and has a low natural abundance. These factors alongwith the fact that living things have not developed a mechanism for converting metallic gold into a soluble form which can be used biochemically, are responsible for making gold not a natural requirement. The Chinese were the first, in 2500 B.C., to administer gold compounds to living beings to produce a therapeutic effect. In early days gold was regarded as a universal cure-all, favourably affecting the course of all diseases. This continued upto late eighteenth century but with no biochemical basis for such treatment. It is not surprising, therefore, that confidence in its use was low.

Gold cyanide, $\text{KAu}(\text{CN})_2$, was observed by Koch¹ to inhibit the growth of *Tubercle bacilli* in the test tube and it is this incident which paved the way for the use of gold salts for the treatment of a number of pathogenic organisms including tuberculosis, syphilis, etc. and put gold therapy on a sound basis. The fortuitous use of gold complexes by Lande² and the improvement of articular manifestations in patients with tuberculosis and coincident rheumatoid arthritis, led Forestier³ in 1929 to use such complexes specifically for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis, although serious toxic and fatal reactions were associated. Subsequently, the use of gold-sulphur complexes was found to be safer though concern regarding their toxicity influenced their dosage and the frequency of administration. A carefully conducted multi-centred study by the Empire Rheumatism Council in the late 1950's established that gold was an effective agent with remittive potential⁴. Now, with increasing knowledge of modern pharmacokinetics and wider experience, gold therapy has become safer and more effective in the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis.

Gold salts and sodium aurosulphite, $\text{Na}_2\text{Au}(\text{SO}_3)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are used against tuberculosis⁵. Gold drugs are preferred⁶ for the treatment of the skin disease *Pemphigus vulgaris*, and *in vitro* tests using gold complexes of sulfamides (I), sulphadiazine, sulphamethizole and sulphasomidine show a higher antimicrobial activity⁷.

The antipyrine complex of gold $[\text{AuCl}_4][\text{HL}]$, has antitumor activities⁸ as also the 5-substituted tetrazole triphenylphosphine gold(I) complexes⁹(II). The antiarthritic drug, (2,3,4,6-tetra-O-acetyl-1-thio- β -D-glucopyranosato-S)(triethylphosphine)gold, auranofin is recently shown to have antitumor properties¹⁰.

Gold drugs against arthritis: The antiarthritic activity of gold(I) compounds may be related to the high affinity, and hence selectivity, of Au^{I} for sulphhydryl S as a biological ligand. It is notable that connective tissue diseases are often accompanied by subnormal levels of serum SH groups and the gold compounds (mainly thiols) in clinical use are potent inhibitors of sulphhydryl-disulphide (SH-SS) exchange reactions¹¹ and can participate in facile sulphhydryl ligand exchange reactions. Gold is now one of the

few drugs that can effectively alter the course of rheumatoid arthritis.

Gold sodium thiosulphate, $\text{Na}_2[\text{Au}(\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2]$, clinically known as Sanocrysin (III) has been used for the treatment of arthritis, tuberculosis and leprosy¹¹.

The drug is administered in aqueous solution through intramuscular or intravenous injections. Gold disodium thiomalate, Na_2Autm , (Myocrisin) (IV) has stood the test of the time in its use against arthritis. A suspension of this compound gives favourable results against chronic rheumatism. Administered parenterally, it suppresses both the primary and secondary lesions while increasing the Au levels, and is effective against adjuvant induced arthritis¹². Gold thioglucose, GTG (Solganol) (V) is widely used against arthritis and seems to be less toxic than Na_2Autm .

A heavy dose (350-500 mg Au/kg body weight) of GTG induces hyperphagia (increased macrophage level), insatiable appetite and obesity in certain strains of mice, but in clinical dose (0.35 mg Au/kg) it is rather safe¹³. It is administered as an oil-suspension intramuscularly, and a depot effect is noticeable. Aqueous solutions of gold thiopolypetides are commercial drugs (Aurodetoxin). Although some patients can safely remain on gold therapy for many years, about 35 percent do suffer from some toxic side-reactions.

Oral gold drugs: Oral drugs are of value in permitting the administration of minimum daily doses and of facilitating the control of both dosage and related toxicity. The known soluble gold drugs given orally provide no protection against adjuvant arthritis and the need for new gold drugs was great. In searching for new oral gold drugs, Sutton and coworkers¹⁴ noted that alkylphosphine gold complexes, R_3PAuX , administered orally, were as effective as other antiinflammatory agents for adjuvant arthritis and harmful retention of gold by kidney is very much reduced. These compounds are highly soluble in lipids and their therapeutic responses seem to be structure-dependent. Although non-gold phosphine compounds gave no protection,

comparative studies indicated that the nature of the phosphine ligand in the gold complexes played a greater role in bringing about changes in biological activity than did the other group (X) bonded directly to Au.

The serum gold levels, as well as the therapeutic effect, were highest with Et_3PAuCl and decreased with increasing bulkiness of the alkyl substituent (Table I).

TABLE I—SERUM GOLD LEVELS AND ANTIARTHRITIC PROPERTIES OF R_3PAuX COMPLEXES

	Serum gold μm day 16	% Reduction of hind leg volume	
		Primary Lesion (injected leg) day 3	Adjuvant arthritis (noninjected leg) day 16
Me_3PAuCl	8	10	—
Et_3PAuCl	27	14	23
$(i\text{-Pr})_3\text{PAuCl}$	17	15	16
$(n\text{-Bu})_3\text{PAuCl}$	5	20	—
Me_3PAuTG	12	14	16
Et_3PAuTG	21	17	—
$(i\text{-Pr})_3\text{PAuTG}$	—	13	15
$(n\text{-Bu})_3\text{PAuTG}$	6	28	—
Et_3PAuATG	21	30	45
$(n\text{-Bu})_3\text{PAuATG}$	6	28	—

The data in Table I show that the highest antiarthritic activity for a constant X moiety (X = halide or sugar-containing thiolate) was obtained for the triethylphosphine complex, compared to the methyl, isopropyl and n-butyl analogues. For the triethylphosphine complexes, the greatest activity was for X = 2,3,4,6-tetraacetyl- β -D-1-thioglucose, which is undergoing clinical trial on human subjects¹⁵. This complex Et_3PAuATG (Auranofin) (VI) has proven much more satisfactory and in rats, oral doses of auranofin produced lower serum and kidney gold levels than the equivalent intramuscular injection of Na_2Autm , and the activity against induced adjuvant arthritis was great.

It was suggested that small daily doses of auranofin maintain a more constant serum gold level and thereby avoid toxic reactions which are caused by large pulses of serum gold, following weekly or monthly Na_2AuTm injections. The dose-related serum gold levels indicate that auranofin is effectively absorbed, and produces significant dose-response suppression of primary and secondary lesions of adjuvant arthritic rats and its antiarthritic potency is equal to or better than injectable Na_2AuTm . Like Na_2AuTm it produces systematic changes including alternation in the circulating antibodies, decreases in rheumatoid factor and increases in albumin levels^{1,5}. Pharmacokinetic studies in normal rats suggest that daily oral chrysotherapy produces a greater stability in blood gold levels and less renal gold accumulation than injectable gold drugs. Auranofin, but not Na_2AuTm inhibits lysosomal enzyme release (and/or decrease in immune complex formation) which explains its therapeutic action. A significant difference between Na_2AuTm and auranofin is that Na_2AuTm does not potentially inhibit the sulphhydryl group reactivity. The predicted value of auranofin in rheumatoid arthritis based on the arthritic and immunological parameters in the *in vivo* and *in vitro* models is borne out in human studies^{1,6}.

upon the mode of administration, the rate of elimination of gold from the body and other factors. The common toxic reactions involve the skin and mucous membrane. Because of their toxicity, gold drugs are not tolerated by aged individuals and by individuals having renal disease, infectious hepatitis, blood dyscrasias, urticaria, eczema and colitis.

Among examples of some other orally administered gold drugs are the bis-coordinated gold(I) salts of the type $[\text{R}_2\text{PAuPR}'_2]^+\text{X}^-$, $(\text{R}_2\text{PAu})_2\text{S}$, $[\text{R}^1\text{R}^2\text{SAuSR}^3\text{R}^4]^+\text{X}^-$, $[\text{Py-Au-Py}]^+\text{X}^-$ (VII) and $[\text{Py-Au-PR}_3]^+\text{X}^-$ (VIII), (where $\text{R}=\text{C}_{1-4}$ alkyl or alkoxy, Ph, halophenyl, C_{1-4} alkoxyphenyl; $\text{X}=\text{ClO}_4$, IO_4 , BF_4 and PF_6) and a novel cyclic phosphorous ylide complex, $[\text{Et}_3\text{PCH}_2\text{AuCH}_2\text{PEt}_3]^+\text{Cl}^-$ (IX).

Gold poisoning and treatment: Most of the effective gold drugs are compounds of S and P containing ligands with Au^I . Pharmacological as well as toxicological studies preclude the use of gold(III) compounds as drugs. Gold(III) compounds are highly toxic, because of their strong oxidising power, greater inhibition of enzymes and greater retention in tissues.

An effective treatment of rheumatoid arthritis with gold drugs results in some degree of clinical toxicity whose severity and extent varies depending

To avoid the serious toxic reactions, chrysotherapy is initiated with small doses of gold and the dose regimen is increased gradually. The therapy is withheld temporarily in case of a serious untoward response. When the toxic reactions are too severe, detoxifying agents (antagonists) such as penicillamine (β , β -dimethyl cysteine), dimercaprol (2,3-dimercaptopropanol, commonly known as British Anti-Lewisite, BAL) (X), antihistamines or adrenocorticosteroids are administered topically¹⁷. Clinical trials of dimercaptosuccinic acid (dms) as an antagonist have recently been suggested¹⁸. It is more water-soluble and less lipid-soluble than BAL, and should favour excretion rather than distribution. These antagonists have the property of reacting with gold to form the tightly bound complexes thereby preventing or reversing the binding of the toxic gold to body ligands, and promoting excretion of gold through urine or faeces.

Conclusion :

The rich coordination chemistry of gold gives rise to a biochemistry that is potentially very complicated. Nevertheless, a wide variety of both physical and chemical techniques are now being applied to this problem to understand the difference in behaviour between the intramuscular and oral gold drugs. Preferred gold drugs are compounds of gold(I). Gold(III) is too toxic to act as a drug. Gold(I) seems to follow the sequence given below as it is distributed through the body and excreted.

Gold-sulphur complexes are more effective and remittive agents for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. They are also beneficial in the treatment of psoriatic arthritis and discoid lupus, pemphigus vulgaris and bronchial asthma. A new compound, auranofin, in which gold is stabilised by both sulphur and phosphorous ligands, is shown to have several advantages over conventional gold-sulphur complexes. The hydrophobic and non-ionic characteristic of auranofin facilitate cell membrane penetration

and thus it is effective at lower blood concentrations, thereby avoiding the serious adverse reactions of gold-sulphur drugs.

The therapeutic potential of the gold complexes is significant and further investigation in this area should be stimulating not only for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis but also for that of a number of other diseases^{19,20}.

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